

Science communicators based at PAN RIs engaged by ExPaNDS

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Abstract

The ExPaNDS project engages science communicators based at Photon and Neutron research infrastructures to create a strong European network so that the collaboration can cascade outputs in a swift and effective way to target audiences.

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Network of communicators

The communicators¹ from the following facilities help us disseminate and are involved in reviewing our deliverables:

Type	Facility	Location
Synchrotrons	SOLEIL	Saclay, France
	Diamond Light Source	Oxfordshire, UK
	Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI)	Villigen, Switzerland
	Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (DESY)	Hamburg, Germany
	ALBA Synchrotron	Barcelona, Spain
	Helmholtz Zentrum Berlin (HZB)	Berlin, Germany
	MAX IV Laboratory	Lund, Sweden
	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste	Trieste, Italy
	ESRF European Synchrotron	Grenoble, France
	Synchrotron SOLARIS	Krakow, Poland
	Helmholtz Zentrum Dresden Rossendorf (HZDR)	Dresden, Germany
FEL	European XFEL	Hamburg, Germany
	FELIX Laboratory	Nijmegen, Netherlands
	Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI)	Villigen, Switzerland
	Helmholtz Zentrum Dresden Rossendorf (HZDR)	Dresden, Germany
	FERMI at Elettra	Trieste, Italy
Neutron facilities	ISIS Pulsed Neutron Source	Oxford, UK
	Institut Laue-Langevin (ILL)	Grenoble, France
	European Spallation Source (ESS)	Lund, Sweden
	Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI)	Villigen, Switzerland
	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB)	Berlin, Germany
Other	ISA Center for Storage Ring Facilities	Aarhus, Denmark
	CERIC-ERIC	Trieste, Italy
	ELI laser facility	Prague, Czech Republic

Most of the ExPaNDS facilities are already members of the collaborations lightsources.org and / or neutrons.org who have been working successfully to communicate about photon and neutron science for over a decade.

The ExPaNDS network of collaborators will be able to use and rely on those existing collaborations to support their work and to disseminate information to their existing communities.

¹ For personal data protection reasons, the name and contact address of the communicators is not provided.

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